

Mapping of textural facies in Europa's chaotic terrain to investigate the physical and chemical factors influencing their formation

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0 750 1500 km

Mercator Projection
Planetographic west longitude coordinate system
Data source: https://astrogeology.usgs.gov/search/map/europa_voyager_galileo_ssi_global_mosaic_500m
Basemaps credits: USGS Astrogeology Science Center

From Disruption to Progressive Fractional Melting (i-iv)

- | | |
|--|---|
| Higher proportion of small-sized blocks versus matrix (iii) |
| Dominance of the matrix fraction (iv) |